

GREEN.DAT.AI

1st Policy Brief

The AI Act and the GREEN.DAT.AI Project: Partners in Responsible AI

This policy brief delves into the essence of the AI Act and explores its connection with the GREEN.DAT.AI project, which develops energy efficient AI tools for data analysis. **Enacted in March 2024**, the **AI Act** establishes comprehensive guidelines for the development and deployment of AI technologies within the EU. By categorizing AI applications into various risk levels - from unacceptable (e.g., social scoring systems) to minimal risk (e.g., spam filters) - the AI Act ensures that each category is regulated according to its potential impact on society. High-risk applications, such as facial recognition systems, are subject to stringent requirements designed to ensure safety, fairness, and transparency. At its core, the AI Act emphasises several key principles:

Transparency

Ensuring that AI decision-making processes are understandable to humans.

Accountability

Mandating that AI developers and users take responsibility for their AI systems.

Security and Functionality

Requiring AI systems to be secure and perform as intended.

Non-discrimination

Prohibiting AI from making biased decisions that could harm individuals or groups.

Human Oversight

Ensuring significant AI-driven decisions involve human intervention to prevent automated harm.

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The **GREEN.DAT.AI project** is a pioneering initiative focused on creating AI tools that are both responsible and environmentally sustainable. The project's alignment with the AI Act is evident through several aspects:

Explainable AI (XAI): GREEN.DAT.AI utilizes XAI to make the decision-making processes of its models transparent and understandable to users.

Privacy Protection: The project employs federated learning, a technique that allows AI to learn from data without compromising user privacy, thus aligning with the AI Act's privacy standards.

Energy Efficiency: One of GREEN.DAT.AI's core objectives is to develop AI technologies that consume less energy, thereby supporting the EU's Green Deal goals for sustainability.

Human-Centric AI: GREEN.DAT.AI designs its AI tools to assist rather than replace human decision-making, promoting a collaborative human-AI interaction model.

The impact on AI development is multifaceted. First, it establishes clear regulatory guidelines for developers and users, ensuring a well-defined framework within which AI technologies can evolve. This clarity in regulations not only promotes responsible AI innovation by addressing and mitigating potential harms but also fosters public trust in AI development and deployment, creating a more secure and reliable technological landscape.

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The AI Act offers several advantages to the GREEN.DAT.AI project, some of the key advantages being:

- i) Market Attractiveness:** Compliance with the AI Act can make GREEN.DAT.AI's products more appealing in the EU market by ensuring they meet high regulatory standards.
- ii) Clear Guidelines:** The Act provides a clear regulatory framework that simplifies the development and deployment processes for GREEN.DAT.AI's tools.
- iii) Public Trust:** Adhering to the AI Act's principles enhances public trust in GREEN.DAT.AI's commitment to ethical and responsible AI development.

Despite the benefits, at the same time there are challenges that GREEN.DAT.AI must navigate:

Increased Complexity

Adhering to the detailed requirements of the AI Act might introduce additional complexity in the development process.

Regulatory Evolution

As the AI Act is relatively new, its provisions and interpretations may evolve, necessitating continuous updates and adaptations from GREEN.DAT.AI to stay compliant.

The GREEN.DAT.AI project exemplifies a commitment to developing AI solutions that align with the EU's vision for responsible and sustainable technology. By adhering to the AI Act, GREEN.DAT.AI ensures that its services are not only eco-friendly but also meet the highest standards of ethics and legality. This alignment positions GREEN.DAT.AI favorably for widespread adoption of its AI solutions across Europe, paving the way for a future where technology and sustainability go hand in hand.

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- Project Coordinator: Ioanna Fergadiotou • Institution: INLECOM INNOVATION • Start: 01/01/2023
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GREENDATAI EU Project

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